

ORTHO-SUBSTITUTED DIPHENYLS. PART III

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o-Phenyl- α : β -dichlorocinnamic acid and *o*-phenyl- ω -chlorostyrene have been prepared. The latter in presence of aluminium chloride has been converted into phenanthrene.

In a preceding paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 381) the preparation of *o*-phenylcinnamic acid (I) was reported. A detailed study of this interesting compound and some of its important derivatives is being made. On observing the structure of this compound containing the *o*-phenylstyrene residue, it becomes obvious that it would lend itself admirably to a new synthesis of phenanthrene which would have certain advantages over a number of other well known syntheses of this hydrocarbon like those of Paschorr (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 496), Bardhan and Sen-Gupta (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2520), and Newman and Farbman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1550). In all these and similar syntheses of phenanthrene, this hydrocarbon is produced as the result of a drastic pyrogenetic treatment either alone or with zinc or selenium of substituted or hydrogenated intermediate derivatives. The present authors have avoided the use of such pyrogenetic methods and have presented a simple and elegant synthesis of phenanthrene, which clearly indicates the structure of the hydrocarbon and affords an easy method for its preparation and for the preparation of its derivatives.

A well powdered suspension of *o*-phenylcinnamic acid in carbon tetrachloride, when saturated with chlorine gas in sunlight, gives the crystalline *o*-phenyl- α : β -dichlorophenylpropionic acid (II). This compound on being boiled with a concentrated solution of sodium carbonate loses a molecule of carbon dioxide and hydrochloric acid each and yields an oily compound which is the *o*-phenyl- ω -chlorostyrene (III). These reactions and the formation of these derivatives are similar to those studied by Liebermann and Finkenbeiner (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2235) and Biltz (*Annalen*, 1897, 296, 266) in the case of cinnamic acid.

If the *o*-phenyl- ω -chlorostyrene could be made to condense with the loss of a molecule of hydrochloric acid, involving the closure of the ring at the point of the *O*-hydrogen atom of the second benzene nucleus of the diphenyl it would result in the formation of phenanthrene (IV). This condensation takes place in the presence of aluminium chloride with or without solvent (ligroin). Along with the phenanthrene produced considerable quantities of a brown plastic substance are also obtained whose nature has not yet been closely investigated. Under the best conditions reported below the yield of phenanthrene is nearly 40%.

If this condensation takes place with the removal of hydrochloric acid from the side chain no ring-closure would occur and *o*-diphenylacetylene (V) would be formed. This

compound has not yet been isolated by us but we suspect that the plastic substance mentioned above is a polymerised product of the acetylene derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Phenyl- α : β -dichlorocinnamic Acid.—To a suspension of well powdered *o*-phenylcinnamic acid (22.4 g., 1/10 mol) in dry carbon tetrachloride (225 g.) a slow current of dry chlorine was passed in sunlight. The suspension was soon coloured yellowish green. The colour, however, was lost soon on account of the absorption of the dissolved chlorine. The operation was repeated till the colour remained permanent which indicated the presence of an excess of chlorine. During the process of absorption of chlorine a stage was reached when considerable heat was generated, the suspension cleared up and the substance went completely into solution. Very soon after, however, precipitation of granular crystals of a different nature began. The mixture was kept overnight when most of the *o*-phenyl- α : β -dichlorophenylpropionic acid was precipitated. This was filtered off and a further quantity recovered by the removal of carbon tetrachloride by distillation. On recrystallisation from benzene colourless granular crystals were obtained, m.p. 164°, yield 26 g. (88%). (Found : Cl, 23.89. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24.04 per cent).

o-Phenyl- ω -chlorostyrene.—*o*-Phenyl- α : β -dichlorocinnamic acid (20 g., 1/15 mol) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of sodium carbonate (7.5 g., 1/15 mol) solution and heated on the water-bath with a reflux condenser for 7 hours during which time an oil was produced. After cooling the oil was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract dried overnight with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was evaporated off and the residue distilled at 145°/2 mm., yield 13.2 g. (91%). (Found : Cl, 16.41. $C_{14}H_{11}Cl$ requires Cl, 16.55 per cent).

Phenanthrene.—Well powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.19 g., 1/700 mol) was gradually added to freshly distilled *o*-phenyl- ω -chlorostyrene (4.3 g., 1/50 mol) kept in a small flask fitted with an air condenser, and thoroughly shaken after each addition. The flask was now placed on a water-bath whose temperature was gradually raised to the boiling point, and the contents frequently well shaken. At 42° (bath temperature) a vigorous reaction occurred suddenly with evolution of a large amount of gas and the mixture darkened considerably. The reaction slowed down after about 10 minutes, but the heating was continued for 7 hours on a boiling water-bath till the evolution of hydrochloric acid ceased completely. The dark mass was now treated with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over calcium chloride and the ether distilled off. The residue was distilled at 145°/0.5 mm., when the colourless oil solidified into colourless crystals on cooling. The solid on recrystallisation with 70% alcohol gave shining flakes of phenanthrene with a blue fluorescence, m.p. 99-100°, yield 1.35 g. (38%).

Phenanthrene was converted into its picrate by the usual method. The picrate on being crystallised from redistilled alcohol gave long yellow needles, m.p. 145° (Found : C, 59.15; H, 2.95. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{15}O_7N_3$: C, 58.97; H, 3.19 per cent). The regenerated phenanthrene had m.p. 99.5° (Found : C, 94.45; H, 5.48. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}$: C, 94.39; H, 5.62 per cent). The identity of phenanthrene and its picrate was confirmed by mixed m.p. with a specimen of pure (Schuchardt) phenanthrene and its picrate.